

ISic3339

Honorific for the Emperor Tiberius

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble (white)

Object

tabula

Editor

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Autopsy

2006.04

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agathyrnum

Place of origin (modern)

Capo d'Orlando

Provenance

Found when digging a well in or before 1882, on the farm of Filippo Cangemi, Capo d'Orlando (Casa Cangemi is marked on the 1:25000 map)

Coordinates

38.13686, 14.73646

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Capo d'Orlando, Antiquarium di Capo
d'Orlando

Physical Description

A rectangular off-white marble slab, broken in three joining fragments, the lower
right corner missing. The reverse is unfinished.

Dimensions

Height 15.1 cm

Width 70.2 cm

Depth 4.9 cm

Layout

Latin text over three lines. The two letters of the third line are centred and
much smaller

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Neat v-cut letters, well, but not perfectly spaced and regular, with deep
triangular
serifs, and deep triangular interpuncts between every
word. Long 'I' is elongated.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 42-61 mm

Line 2: 41-43 mm

Line 3: 15 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation not measured: mm

Text

1. Ti (berio) · Caesari · divi · f (ilio) · Augusto
2. P (ublius) · Clodius · C (ai) · f (ilius) · Rufus · Latro p (ecunia) ş (ua)
3. f (aciendum) · c (uravit) ·

Apparatus

Salinas 1884 reports four fragments and reads the end of line 2 as intact; the fourth

fragment appears to be now lost, but the tops of both the reported P and S are still visible.

Translation (en)

For Tiberius Caesar, son of the divine Augustus. Publius Clodius Rufus Latro, son of Gaius took care
of making this with his own money.

Commentary

This is the only known inscription from the immediate area of Capo d'Orlando (probably ancient Agathyrnum).

Digital identifiers:

TM 492390

EDCS 34100466

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
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Henzen, W., Zangemeister, K. F. W. 1872-1913. *Ephemeris epigraphica. Corporis inscriptionum Latinarum supplementum*, edita iussu Instituti archaeologici Romani. Berlin. At VIII 708

Spigo, U. 2004. *Archeologia a Capo d'Orlando: studi per l'Antiquarium*. Milazzo. At 40-42 ph

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3339. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358221>

Photo J. Prag